

IMAGE

Sinoatrial Nodal Artery Occlusion During a Left-Sided Atrial Tachycardia Ablation

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The proximity to vascular structures is a limiting factor during radiofrequency ablation.¹ Major atrial coronary arteries, including the sinoatrial node artery (SNA), were commonly found in or crossing the areas involved in left-sided atrial ablations with significant caliber.²

A 52-year-old woman with a previous mitral valve replacement was referred for atrial tachycardia ablation. She underwent an electrophysiological study, which revealed a perimitral clockwise flutter. We decided to perform an anteroseptal mitral isthmus line between the right superior pulmonary vein and the septal mitral annulus (Figure 1). However, suddenly, asystole developed during the ablation procedure. Coronary angiography was performed due to suspicion of possible injury to the

SNA; angiography demonstrated the subtotal acute occlusion of the SNA originated unusually from the left circumflex artery fluoroscopically close to the successful ablation site (Figure 2). Energy delivery was immediately terminated, but asystole persisted for 11 seconds followed by sinus bradycardia. SNA flow was significantly slow at the termination site and was graded as Thrombolysis In Myocardial Infarction (TIMI) flow grade 0-1 (Video 1). We could not cross the lesion by 0.014 floppy wire due to the sharp angle (Video 2). However, 10 minutes later, after a 200 µg intracoronary nitroglycerine injection, the flow was restored to TIMI flow grade 2 (Video 3). Therefore, the asystole was self-healing, and no complications were seen in the following follow-up. Acute or sub-acute sinus node dysfunction has only recently been suggested as a potential complication of mitral anteroseptal line or cardioneuroablation.^{3,4} Furthermore, asystolic pauses have been observed during RF ablation of left ventricular free-wall accessory pathways, slow AV node pathways, and the left superior pulmonary vein.⁵⁻⁷ It should be kept in mind, in particular, during ablations of left-sided atrial tachyarrhythmias.

You can access the videos mentioned in the article at the following address.

<https://jaejournalvideos.com.bilkentaritmi.com.tr/a3videos.html>

Figure 1. Three-dimensional mapping shows the anteroseptal line.

Figure 2. Angiography reveals acute subtotal occlusion of the sinus node artery.

References

1. Pardo Meo J, Scanavacca M, Sosa E, et al. Atrial coronary arteries in areas involved in atrial fibrillation catheter ablation. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol*. 2010;3(6):600-605.
2. Baskovski E, Candemir B, Kozluca V. Sinoatrial Node Artery Injury During Left Atrial Tachycardia Ablation. *JACC Clin Electrophysiol*. 2020;6(8):1048-1049.

3. Barra S, Gopalan D, Baran J, Fynn S, Heck P, Agarwal S. Acute and sub-acute sinus node dysfunction following pulmonary vein isolation: a case series. *Eur Heart J Case Rep.* 2018;2(1):ytx020.
4. Scanavacca M, Rivarola EWR, Torres RVA, et al. Sinus Node Artery Occlusion During Cardiac Denervation Procedures. *JACC Case Rep.* 2022;4(18):1169-1175.
5. Nantsupawat T, Krishnappa D, Benditt DG. Sinus arrest: A rare observation during radiofrequency ablation along the coronary sinus roof. *Ann Noninvasive Electrocardiol.* 2021;26(1):e12772.
6. Hu HS, Xue M, Xu R, Wang XJ, Chen MY, Yan SH. Sudden asystole during radiofrequency ablation: a case report and literature review. *BMC Res Notes.* 2014;7:351.
7. Rivarola EW, Hachul D, Wu T, et al. Targets and End Points in Cardiac Autonomic Denervation Procedures. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol.* 2017;10(2):e004638.

Informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interests

None

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